

Deep learning based soft-sensor for continuous chlorophyll estimation on decentralized data

Judith Sáinz-Pardo Díaz, María Castrillo^{*}, Álvaro López García

Instituto de Física de Cantabria (IFCA), CSIC-UC, Avda. Los Castros s/n, Santander (Cantabria) 39005, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Chlorophyll monitoring
Water quality
Soft sensor
Deep learning
Federated learning

ABSTRACT

Monitoring the concentration of pigments like chlorophyll (Chl) in water-bodies is a key task to contribute to their conservation. However, with the existing sensor technology, measurement in real-time and with enough frequency to ensure proper risk management is not completely feasible. In this work, with the concept of data-driven soft-sensing, three hydrophysical features are used together with three meteorological ones to estimate the concentration of Chl in two tributaries of the River Thames. Data driven models, specifically neural networks, are used with three learning approaches: individual, centralized and federated. Data reduction scenarios are proposed in order to analyze the performance of each approach when less data is available. The best results in the training are usually obtained with the individual approach. However, the federated learning provides better generalization ability. It was also observed that in most of the cases the results of the federated learning approach improve those of the centralized one.

1. Introduction

Freshwater is an essential resource for life, given that human well-being and ecosystems health depend on the quality and availability of water. However, water bodies are increasingly coming under pressure, leading to water scarcity and a deterioration in water quality. In particular, climate change, unpredictable weather patterns and droughts are contributing significantly to the strain on the availability of freshwater arising from urban development and agriculture (Visser et al., 2016; Glibert 2020). Among the issues concerning water quality degradation, nutrient pollution causing excessive growth of algae, a phenomenon called eutrophication, poses a significant challenge to the management of inland water bodies, threatening the availability of safe drinking water. Eutrophication and Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) suppose not only environmental, but also societal and economic problems, that are taking place in many natural and artificial water-bodies around the world, like rivers, lakes and reservoirs (Jin et al., 2019; Barros et al., 2019).

Monitoring plays a key role in the contribution to water sustainability, helping not only to ensure the compliance with limit values, but also to trigger immediate responses as well as for validation of the control measures in place, among other applications (Chorus and Welker 2021). Recently, the last United Nations' (UN) report (United Nations

and Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2022) about the global progress on the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development has recognized that the lack of monitoring, especially in the poorest countries, is limiting the identification of water quality issues at an early stage, and therefore the implementation of mitigation measures before severe deterioration occurs. However, with the existing sensor technology a lot of crucial parameters (*i.e.* nutrients, pigments, micropollutants, etc.) cannot be monitored in real-time and with enough frequency to ensure proper risk management. In the case of HABs, to date there exists barriers to detect them even at the first level of an early warning system: the quantification of biological activity (Almuhtaram et al., 2021). Algae and cyanobacteria automatic monitoring has been generally carried out by means of *in vivo* fluorometry, which quantifies the concentration of pigments like chlorophyll (Chl) and phycocyanin. *In situ* submersible fluorometers directly measure the fluorescence of the pigments present in cells, being able to easily collect large amounts of data and to make vertical and horizontal profiling. For some applications, the fluorescence measures may be enough, while for others a correlation with *in vitro* measures is required, in order to convert fluorescence data into biomass concentration and to determine the range of application of the fluorometer. In any case, portable fluorometers are not economical sensors and require proper maintenance due to dirtying of the optical components, constricting the deployment of multiple sensors to cover the

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: castrillo@ifca.unican.es (M. Castrillo).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2023.120726>

Received 20 April 2023; Received in revised form 8 September 2023; Accepted 9 October 2023

Available online 14 October 2023

0043-1354/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

variability of a water mass (in depth or in surface) and restricting their use to accessible areas to ensure regular maintenance. An alternative is the use of data mining (DM) and machine learning (ML) models to perform high frequency monitoring. These techniques allow exploiting the relationship between a target variable and other parameters or surrogates that can be easily and continuously measured with a high time resolution by means of robust and affordable sensors. The software-based sensor that processes the available surrogate data by means of models and allows inferring the target variable(s) is called a *soft-sensor*. In the field of artificial intelligence (AI), the models that conform the soft-sensor are data-driven models. Suitable surrogates are mainly hydrophysical indicators like temperature, pH, electric conductivity (EC), turbidity, etc.

In recent years, different types of soft-sensors have been developed with the purpose of monitoring water quality parameters (Castrillo and López García 2020; Nair et al., 2022). These types differ in the target variable (nutrients, Chl, bacteria, etc.), the number and nature of the surrogates and in the implemented algorithms (regression trees, support vector regression (SVR) different architectures of artificial neural networks (ANN), etc.). Regarding Chl estimation, ML has been mostly applied to exploit spectral data and other water quality indicators as proxies (Khruschev et al., 2022). Among them, (García Nieto et al. 2019) developed ML models based on physical–chemical parameters and different algal species counts. In (Park et al., 2015) authors developed an early-warning protocol based on ML models, but they rely on variables (nutrient concentrations) that are not easy to obtain with high-resolution in the long term, as well as in (Kim and Ahn 2022). Recently, (Mozo et al., 2022) applied ML models (Classification and Regression Trees and Random Forests (RF) regressor) for algal bloom predictions using only basic and commonplace sensors as surrogates in two sampling points of a reservoir, demonstrating its feasibility as low-cost and energy-efficient soft-sensor. However, the error of the ML models was high if it is compared with the average values of the Chl concentrations. (Barzegar et al., 2020) implemented a hybrid convolutional neural network (CNN) - long short-term memory (LSTM) model to predict Chl-a concentrations using pH, oxidation–reduction potential (ORP), water temperature, EC and their $t-1$ and $t-2$ lags as predictor variables. Recently, a different approach for high-frequency and real-time monitoring of phytoplankton blooms has been presented, making use of measurements of the spectral reflectance properties of the water body (Wang et al., 2021).

A very common inconvenient in ML processes is the absence of enough data to train the models. Since the measurement of the target variables is usually an expensive and time-consuming task, the water masses monitoring datasets are not as large as AI algorithms training requires, which can be in the range of thousands or more observations. Additionally, environmental agencies or companies in charge of water masses monitoring usually take measures from different points of the mass in order to cover the variability that characterizes them due to hydrodynamic conditions, the location of discharge points, etc. Given that one of the drawbacks of ML models can be the lack of generalization, which makes them site-specific, gathering the data from different points all together may result in general models with low accuracy. A possible solution to this issue can be merging the individual models instead of gathering the data together. This approach is called *federated learning* (FL) (McMahan et al., 2017). FL emerges as a technique to build a centralized model when data is distributed and cannot be centralized due to privacy or security issues, or technical constraints (lack of data storage, lack of network connectivity, etc.). We are not aware of any other environmental study where FL has been implemented.

This work presents the design and development of soft-sensors for the estimation of Chl concentration relying only in basic hydrophysical variables, as well as in open-access meteorological ones. The latter, besides being important factors influencing primary growth (Shuvo et al., 2021), are potentially available in real time and there exists worldwide databases where data can be obtained to train the models. It

was hypothesized that meteorological data could enhance the estimation of Chl, as sunlight is one of the main components to enable algal growth and wind speed has demonstrated to be relevant (Aláez et al., 2021) as it is related to the availability of nutrients. With the aim of improving the performance and the generalization ability of the models, three ML training paradigms were considered: the individual approach, which only makes use of data from a specific site, as well as two other approaches, the centralized and federated ones, that broaden the casuistry from which the model learns. Given the large amount of data per site that was available in this use case, different data reduction scenarios were designed, in order to test the different paradigms on more realistic scenarios, especially when the data are obtained by means of manual sampling. It was hypothesized that as the available data per site was reduced, the individual models performance would be worse but the combination with other site's model could improve it.

The content of this work is structured as follows: the methods employed, including the data used, its preprocessing, analysis and management of outliers, as well as the description of the ML paradigms and architectures of the models are detailed in Section 2. Section 3 provides a detailed analysis and discussion of the results obtained and, finally, Section 4 presents the conclusions reached together with a proposal for future work.

2. Methods

2.1. Data availability and curation

This work was carried out using an open-access dataset containing information about two tributaries of the River Thames (England): the *River Enborne* and *The Cut*. Two data files with information about the two tributaries were obtained from the Environmental Information Data center platform¹ of the center for Ecology and Hydrology (CEH) belonging to the United Kingdom's Natural Environment Research Council. This use case presents two zones with quite different conditions: while the River Enborne is relatively rural, The Cut is in an urbanized catchment. Both files contained hourly data from around two years (from November 2009 to February 2012 in the case of the River Enborne and from May 2010 to February 2012 in the case of The Cut) of the following hydrophysical and chemical variables: Chl concentration ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), turbidity (NTU), EC ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$), water temperature (Temp) ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), pH, dissolved oxygen concentration (mg L^{-1}), percentage saturation of dissolved oxygen (%) and flow rate ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$). From these variables, we selected three hydrophysical ones (Temp, pH and EC) as features of the models, as we considered them the easiest to collect due to the robustness and ubiquity of the sensors that register them. The selected variables keep a close relationship with Chl concentration, as can be briefly represented by the following factors. Temp affects the degradation and solubility of various nutrient compounds, as well as the kinetic parameters of algal metabolism. pH determines the solubility of carbon dioxide and minerals in water and directly or indirectly influences metabolism. Finally, the EC is a proxy for the nutrient concentrations (Castrillo and López García 2020) available for algal growth. Regarding the remaining variables that we have not considered in our approach, dissolved oxygen is usually measured through optical sensors, which are more sensitive to dirtying and therefore prone to drift. Flow rate or velocity are not easily measured and only available in certain points of rivers. Although in this particular case they were available, the objective is to design models that, besides performing properly, could be transferred or adapted to other cases.

Besides hydrophysical data, three meteorological variables were added: global irradiance (*Global*) (W m^{-2}), air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 2 m above the ground (*T2m*) and wind speed (m s^{-1}) at 10 m above the ground (*WS10m*). These data were obtained from the Photovoltaic

¹ <http://eidc.ceh.ac.uk/>

Fig. 1. Outliers detection of the Chl concentrations for rivers Enborne and The Cut.

Geographical Information System (PVGIS)² which provides hourly data based on data from satellites and reanalysis for given location and dates. Part of the interest in the use of these variables relies on the fact that they are openly and freely available for any point of use.

The hydrophysical data of the River Enborne and The Cut had been already curated by the CEH and the University of Reading (Wade et al., 2012). Initially, 20,412 observations were available for the River Enborne and 15,636 for The Cut. However, after removing the missing values (NaN), these were reduced to 18,850 and 14,162 records in each

case respectively.

In order to detect possible anomalous values that may damage the accuracy of the models, a study of the outliers was performed. Although there exist numerous methods to detect anomalous values on data series, one can run the risk of deleting data that could provide valuable information to the models. In this case, it is interesting to detect non-natural outliers, that is to say, those that may have been produced by different failures in the measuring procedure, as natural outliers could represent the occurrence of an algal bloom. Regarding the predictors, firstly visually detection using line time series plots and box plots for each variable was performed. Then, the InterQuartile Range (IQR) technique or Tukey's test was implemented as follows: be Q_i for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ the

² https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/en/

Fig. 2. Violin plots with the features distribution for the rivers Enborne and The Cut. Train and test splits.

three data quartiles, then the lower and upper limits established are presented below:

$$lower\ limit = Q_1 - 3(Q_3 - Q_1)$$

$$upper\ limit = Q_1 + 3(Q_3 - Q_1)$$

Those values below and above the lower and upper boundaries respectively were considered outliers. Just a few outliers were found in the River Enborne (4 in the pH time series and 2 in the WS10m's one) and some more in The Cut (171 in the EC time series and 24 in the pH's one). Considering the large amount of data that is handled in this work, the outliers were directly removed, as the outliers of each variable entailed less than 1 % of the observations. Regarding the target variable, Chl concentration, deleting exceptionally high values that could be attributed to an algal bloom would be detrimental to the performance of the soft-sensors. As an absolute value of Chl may be perfectly feasible, the focus was put on the change rate with respect to the previous value, which can give more information about the feasibility of a value. In addition, transforming the Chl concentration into Chl growth rates, considering an exponential behavior, results in a transformation of the

distribution of the variable, becoming normal. This allowed implementing parametric methods, as the Tukey's one. Considering x_t the value at instant of time t , t_i and t_j two consecutive time instants ($t_i > t_j$), the growth rate of x is calculated as follows:

$$growth\ rate = \frac{\ln(x_{t_i}) - \ln(x_{t_j})}{t_i - t_j} \tag{1}$$

Once the growth rate had been calculated according to Eq. (1), the Tukey's test was applied and eventually the detected outliers were removed. This process was repeated as many times as necessary so that there were no more outliers to eliminate, recalculating the new growth rates, and considering the lower and upper limits calculated with the initial data distribution.

Fig. 1 shows the time series with the Chl concentration as well as the outliers detected with the criteria indicated above in the first round. This figure shows that certain high peaks in both cases are not detected as outliers according to this criterion, for example, in the case of The Cut, the peak around observation 2000 stands out. Note that the IQR technique and Tukey's tests are applied to Chl growth rates, and not directly

Table 1

Statistics associated to each parameter for the rivers Enborne and The Cut.

Ecosystem	Statistics	Parameters						
		EC ($\mu S\ cm^{-1}$)	Temp ($^{\circ}C$)	pH	Global ($W\ m^{-2}$)	WS10m ($m\ s^{-1}$)	T2m ($^{\circ}C$)	Chl ($\mu g\ L^{-1}$)
River Enborne (18,636 records)	Min	215.00	0.20	7.24	0.00	1.45	-2.07	0.50
	Max	769.00	19.50	8.94	944.01	12.62	25.81	17.10
	Mean	476.58	10.27	7.97	431.17	5.36	12.95	3.45
	Std	77.64	4.25	0.22	238.41	1.72	5.83	1.56
River The Cut (13,928 record)	Min	329.00	1.70	7.23	0.00	1.45	-0.93	0.20
	Max	1877.00	22.90	8.39	924.01	11.24	27.28	92.90
	Mean	959.06	12.68	7.71	435.53	5.17	14.10	4.64
	Std	117.87	4.54	0.13	247.68	1.67	6.38	4.75

to Chl concentration data, in order to avoid the removal of Chl peaks that may represent an algal bloom. We are only interested in removing non-natural outliers, that is to say, those that may have been produced by different failures in the measuring procedure, as natural outliers could represent the occurrence of an algal bloom. According to this criterion, as high as a Chl concentration value might be, it should be only considered as an outlier if the increment from the previous value is not considered feasible, and this can be evaluated applying the tests on the growth rate values (considering an exponential growth), instead of directly on the concentration values. For example, what happens in The Cut near observation 2000 is not an increment from 0 to 90 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in one time step, indeed it goes from 6.9 to 92.9 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in 17 time steps. The method finds outside the limits the growth rate occurred in three of these, that are marked in red in Fig. 1, but the growth rate in the last step (from 66 to 92.9) is not considered an outlier.

Regarding the three meteorological features, they were aggregated taking the maximum in the last 24 h for each observation, representing the extreme conditions each day. It was made like this because the meteorological situation is likely to exert a delayed effect on the algal growth. For example, the wind blowing across the water surface pushes the water from the upper layer away while deeper water rises, but this takes time to occur. In Fig. 2 the distribution of the six features that were used to train the models is shown respectively once the data have been processed following the steps described above.

Finally, Table 1 shows different statistics associated with the features presented in Fig. 2, as well as the target variable, calculated after processing the data.

A flowchart to support the understanding of the data pre-processing as well as the training, validation and testing processes explained in the following section, is provided in Fig. 10 in the Appendix.

2.2. Deep learning models

Within the diversity of ML techniques, deep learning (DL) is a methodology that allows the creation of computational models with multiple levels of abstraction (LeCun et al., 2015). In this work ANN were used, which are supervised DL algorithms of great relevance in the state of the art, and which have gained significant popularity with numerous fields of application in recent years (Hinton et al., 2012; Krizhevsky et al., 2017). The concept of *perceptron* or *artificial neuron* mathematically simulates the behavior of a biological neuron to some extent: a stimulus/input is received, which is processed to produce an output. DL-ANN consist of multiple hidden layers, which means that the output of some neurons are the input of others. In addition, a weight associated to each input is calculated and then, the product of each input and its associated weight (plus a bias) is added. Finally, an activation function must be applied to obtain the output (the prediction).

The ANN architecture implemented in this work includes *dense* and *dropout* layers. Dense layers are those in which each neuron in a layer is connected to all the outputs of the previous layer, while dropout layers are used to prevent overfitting and they work by randomly setting the inputs to 0 with a given frequency rate at each step during the training. As activation function, we have used the widely known Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU). This function transforms the negative values to 0 while the positive values are not modified ($f(x) = \max(0, x)$). This architecture has been selected after analyzing different configurations, varying the number of layers, as well as the number of neurons in each one, the rate in the caps dropout, the inclusion of regularization, the optimizer used and its learning rate, as well as the batch size (finally set to 128), among other factors.

The ANN were compiled using the *RMSprop* optimizer with 1×10^{-3} as learning rate and the Mean Squared Error (MSE) as loss function. The Mean Relative Error (MRE) was used as metric to evaluate the performance of the models. Although the use of other error metrics such as MAE was considered, MSE seemed to us the most appropriate due to its

higher penalty on the peaks (as it takes the square of the error). Be $y \in R^n$ the real value and $\bar{y} \in R^n$ the output obtained with the trained model. Then, the MSE and MRE are defined as follows:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2,$$

$$MRE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|y_i - \bar{y}_i|}{y_i}.$$

- Dense layer with 128 neurons. Activation: ReLU. Input shape: number of features.
- Dropout layer with rate 0.4.
- Dense layer with 64 neurons. Activation: ReLU.
- Dropout layer with rate 0.2.
- Dense layer with 32 neurons. Activation: ReLU.
- Dropout layer with rate 0.1.
- Dense layer with 16 neurons. Activation: ReLU.
- Dense layer with 1 neuron (the output). Activation: ReLU.

2.2.1. Individual learning (IL)

The first decision that naturally arises when facing environmental ML models is to train using the data from each sampling area independently, due to the site dependence that characterizes ML models. That is, in the case of the rivers Enborne and The Cut, the models are trained individually with data from each river. Thus, two models are obtained and evaluated on data from each river independently.

To do so, the last 20 % was kept apart as test set (unseen data to test the models once trained). From the other 80 %, the last 15 % was used as validation set while the rest was used as training set. The proposed models were initially trained on the training set for 500 epochs and considering a batch size of 128, taking the validation set for quality control through the observation of the loss function. The number of epochs at which the optimum of the loss function is reached (the lowest MSE in the validation set, but also looking at the performance in the train set) is kept to train the models with the whole available data (training + validation). Finally, the models are tested using the test set.

Regarding data scaling, the same process was followed in both cases using *sklearn MinMaxScaler*: the scaler was *fit* and applied individually to each training set. Subsequently, the test dataset was *transformed* using the corresponding adjusted scaler.

2.2.2. Centralized learning (CL)

In the case where no additional privacy or technical restrictions apply to the data, another approach that emerges intuitively is to train the model on data from both zones gathered together. Especially in this case where the data are taken from two rivers with quite different environmental conditions, it is of special interest to test this approach to build a more general model. In this approach, each data partition for both rivers were joined together, but the models were tested on the test data from each river separately. As in the previous approach, the models were initially trained during 500 epochs and considering a batch size of 128. Again, the validation set was used as reference to obtain the optimum number of epochs to train the model with the whole available training data.

It is important to note that in order not to train with biased data so that there is an imbalance whereby too much data from one river falls in the train relative to the other, the same train-validation-test split described in the previous approach (IL) was performed on both rivers before centralizing the data.

In this case, the scaler was fitted with the centralized training data, and afterwards, it was applied to the case of each test set individually.

2.2.3. Federated learning (FL)

FL is a collaborative and decentralized approach to ML, based on the idea of data decentralization. It is therefore a privacy-preserving ML technique (PPML) (Sáinz-Pardo Díaz and López García 2023). The term FL was first introduced in 2017 by McMahan (McMahan et al., 2017), and is currently experiencing an important upswing (Li et al., 2021). In particular, horizontal FL consists of allowing collaboration between different parties, called clients, that have data with the same features so that they do not have to share their data among themselves, but rely on a central server that supports the process in order to allow collaboration. The process can be summarized in the following steps: (1) the central server creates (after consensus) a model and distributes it to the clients; (2) the clients train the model with their data locally; (3) the clients send to the server the weights obtained after the training; (4) the server aggregates the weights to create a new global model; (5) the server re-distributes among the clients this new global model, and this process is repeated from step 2 as many rounds as it is considered necessary (Sáinz-Pardo Díaz and López García 2023).

In this use case there are two potential clients: each one of the rivers. Specifically, the same model introduced previously was applied but implementing the FL approach. The model was trained in each client for a certain number of epochs N_e , and the scheme was repeated for a number of rounds N_r . Three casuistry were considered: $N_e \in \{10, 50, 100\}$, and associated to each of them a maximum of $N_r = 500 / N_e$ training rounds. The number of rounds of the scheme was optimized according to the MSE obtained for the validation and train sets of each client. In the same way, the number of training epochs was selected among the three analyzed using the validation MSE, seeking a balance between the two rivers. As in the CL approach, the model was tested with the test set from each river independently.

2.3. Data reduction scenarios

In order to analyze the performance of each learning paradigm in more realistic cases, where less data is available, several data reduction scenarios were designed. The first one consists of taking only the data that has been captured on the same dates in both rivers, equalizing the size of the datasets, thus avoiding the effect of the amount of data. Another scenario simulated a situation in which only daily data is available, resampling data taken every day at 8 a.m. Finally, the third scenario simulated weekly data, resampling one data per week from the previous dataset.

2.4. Features importance

In order to check whether the meteorological variables contribute to the performance of the models, two signs were studied: the variation in the error of the models and the Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) values (Lundberg and Lee 2017). The Shapley values are a way to compute how much each variable has contributed to the actual prediction in comparison to the average prediction. The SHAP are useful to quantify feature importance, considering that the features with the largest mean absolute Shapley values are the most important. Specifically, the SHAP values assign to each feature the change in the expected model forecast when conditioned on that feature (Lundberg and Lee 2017). For this calculation, the Python library *shap*³ has been used (version 0.42.1).

3. Results and discussion

In this section the main results for each scenario are presented in terms of the MRE for both train and test sets and for each learning approach.

Table 2

Summary of results in terms of MRE for train and test with the three approaches and using three features.

Approach	Enborne		The Cut	
	MRE (train)	MRE (test)	MRE (train)	MRE (test)
IL	0.16	0.19	0.56	0.17
CL	0.21	0.18	0.65	0.17
FL	0.19	0.17	0.40	0.23

Table 2 shows the results for the case where the input are the three hydro-physical variables mentioned in Section 2.1: EC, Temp and pH. For the FL case the results are shown for the number of epochs in which the optimum is reached for the validation set for each river (verifying $N_r \leq 500/N_e$). Specifically, the third row of Table 2 shows the optimum for both Enborne and The Cut validation sets because in this case it occurred with the same number of epochs in both rivers. The results show that in both cases the scenario in which the model is trained for 50 epochs is more suitable, and for the same number of repetitions (rounds) in each zone (9).

The results presented in Table 2 show that in the case of River Enborne the best approach in the training phase was the IL, however, when it was trained in a FL scheme with The Cut, although the training error was slightly worse, the test error improved. In the case of The Cut, the training error with the IL and the CL approaches were notably high, which to some extent was expected as already occurred with the nutrients estimations in a previous study using the same data (Castrillo and López García 2020). Additionally, the statistics presented in Table 1 show that the maximum value for the Chl concentration ($92.90 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) is far from the mean value ($4.64 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), revealing that there must exist a peak that may have caused the high error. This is graphically shown in Fig. 1, where the peak is seen around observation 2000. However, the test error in these cases was lower, which is attributable to the absence of such high peaks in the test set. The FL approach had different effects in River Enborne and The Cut. In the first case the train error was not as low as with the IL, but the test error was lower, avoiding the overfitting to the train fraction obtained with the IL. On the contrary, in The Cut the FL approach did not provide any advantage in terms of the performance of the model for the test, but a large reduction of the train error and a better balance between these two is reached.

The SHAP values obtained with the four approaches analyzed (IL, CL and FL) are shown in Fig. 3. In particular, EC is the more relevant feature independently of the learning paradigm in the case of River Enborne. It is also the more relevant in The Cut for the IL and FL paradigms, but closely followed by Temp, which is the more relevant for the CL approach in this river. According to Fig. 2 Temp is the variable that shows more difference between the two rivers, and the CL approach seems to rely on this variable to assign the intrinsic characteristics of each river.

Finally, in order to analyze the performance of the predictions on the test set in a more visual way, Fig. 4 shows the predictions obtained for the test sets of both rivers and the observed values. In both cases it can be observed that the centralized model creates peaks (especially in the first observations in both rivers), while it is not able to reproduce accurately the significant peaks that are present in both rivers in the first 500 observations. Motivated by these inaccuracies, the meteorological variables were added in order to enhance the models.

Then, following the same scheme, Table 3 shows the results obtained when the meteorological variables are added. Addition error metrics are given in Table 7 in the Appendix. For the FL approach, the optimum for River Enborne is shown in the third row while the optimum for The Cut is shown in the fourth row. In both cases the model has been trained during 10 epochs but different number of rounds (50 for Enborne and 40 for The Cut). The optimum of the validation MSE was obtained for Enborne with $N_e = 10$, while an improvement was obtained for The Cut with $N_e = 100$. However, since the evolution of the validation seemed

³ <https://github.com/shap/shap>

Fig. 3. Mean of the absolute value of the SHAP values obtained for each feature with the four different approaches exposed in Table 2 for each river (3 features).

Fig. 4. Prediction obtained for the test set of rivers Enborne and The Cut with each model analyzed using three features.

Table 3
Summary of results in terms of MRE for train and test with the three approaches and using six features.

Approach	Enborne		The Cut	
	MRE (train)	MRE (test)	MRE (train)	MRE (test)
IL	0.15	0.18	0.36	0.21
CL	0.20	0.18	0.45	0.19
FL (Enborne)	0.18	0.19	0.39	0.26
FL (The Cut)	0.19	0.18	0.39	0.26

clearer with $N_e = 10$ than in the cases where the model is trained for 50 and 100 epochs, we have selected this first scenario (in addition to the fact that in the production use case it makes more sense to train the same number of epochs in both cases, in order to perform the training once). It should be noted that the results obtained in terms of training and test in each of these three cases (varying the number of epochs) were very similar.

In view of Table 3, first of all it can be seen that the inclusion of the meteorological variables had a positive impact in the train set, especially in the IL and CL approaches in The Cut (see the train MRE). This is also supported by the SHAP values. Fig. 5 shows the mean of the absolute values of the SHAP values for each feature and each learning paradigm. It can be seen that with the IL and the CL approaches in The Cut, the meteorological variables have a high impact, on the contrary than in River Enborne. However, in the FL approaches, EC and Temp are the most significant features in both rivers. A possible explanation is that, as the rivers are close to each other, the meteorological variables

distribution is very similar (as shown in Fig. 2) and the FL approach does not obtain relevant information from them to differentiate each site.

In accordance with this reduction in the train error of all the approaches in The Cut, the best results for this river are those obtained with CL for train and with IL for the test set. Additionally, the best results for River Enborne were achieved through the IL for the train test but with the IL, CL and FL schemes for the test set, the latter providing a better balance between the errors of the two splits.

In order to visualize the performance of the models along the time line in the test sets we have plotted the observed Chl values together with those predicted with each approach in Fig. 6, making zoom in some specific areas to show the forecast both in stable regions and in the peaks. Note that for the FL case only the model obtained for the optimum in the validation set of each river is shown. The same is shown in Fig. 11 in the Appendix for both training sets. In view of Fig. 6, it is remarkable that the prediction with the FL approach is smoother than that obtained with the other learning approaches. This fact resulted in the underestimation of several prominent peaks but a much more accurate prediction in stable periods, although still being able to represent the occurrence of peaks. On the contrary, both the individual and the centralized approaches present more fluctuating predictions, and in the case of River Enborne they tend to overestimate the predictions and produce some peaks that are not seen in the observed values, as in the cases shown in the enlarged views. For the test set of Enborne, in the enlarged section on the left it can be seen that the IL captures the magnitude of the peak better than the FL one, although this approach is also able to reproduce it (although at a lower magnitude than the real one). In the enlarged section of the right (around the observation 3100) it can be observed that IL and FL are able to detect the presence of the peak better than CL.

Fig. 5. Mean of the absolute value of the SHAP values obtained for each feature with the four different approaches exposed in Table 3 for each river.

In the case of The Cut, in the flat periods all the models tend to underestimate the predictions. Additionally, between the observations 1000 and 1500 there is a sharp peak followed by a stepped descent, where only the IL approach is able to get close to the peak. The data have been checked in order to elucidate the reason of this mismatching and it was found that this peak was characterized by an unusual low EC and high WS10m. In particular, when the peak reached its maximum ($11.9 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) the EC was $579 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ and the WS10m had reached 10.28 m s^{-1} in the last 24 h. If we compare with the values shown in Fig. 2 it can be confirmed that these values are scarcely represented in the data, being in the very low range of EC values and in the very high range of WS10m values. The second period of mismatching is around the observation 2500. This period is characterized by a continuous high EC, with values

above $1000 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ that are not well represented in the training fraction of the data. In the case of The Cut and first zoom made in the figure, it can be seen how the models are able to reproduce such peak, as well as its subsequent downward zone and stability.

3.1. Data reduction

In order to study the performance of each learning approach when not massive data are available, the results of the data reduction scenarios are shown in the following paragraphs. The distribution of the data in the data reduction scenarios is shown in the violin plots in Fig. 12 in the Appendix. First of all, as in the case of the River Enborne initially there were 18,636 observations available, while in the case of The Cut there

Fig. 6. Prediction obtained for the test set of rivers Enborne and The Cut with each model analyzed using six features.

Table 4

Summary of results in terms of MRE for train and test with the three approaches and using six features in a scenario with the data reduced to coincident dates in both sites.

Approach	Enborne		The Cut	
	$(n_t = 10,368)$		$(n_t = 10,368)$	
	MRE (train)	MRE (test)	MRE (train)	MRE (test)
IL	0.13	0.20	0.44	0.20
CL	0.19	0.22	0.40	0.19
FL (Enborne)	0.19	0.18	0.40	0.24
FL (The Cut)	0.19	0.17	0.39	0.22

were fewer observations (13,928), the first scenario consisted in equalize both datasets by taking only the observations that were taken in common dates. This scenario was intended to avoid the possible influence of the number of data in the proposed models. It should be remarked that the data from November 2009 to May 2010 in River Enborne are eliminated in this scenario, as these dates were not available in The Cut. This reduces the variability of data in the Enborne’s

dataset, as practically the first half of a water year is removed. With this reduction both datasets have 12,960 observations, which implies a reduction of 30.5% in *River Enborne* and 6.9 % in *The Cut*. The results obtained as MRE of train and test are shown in Table 4, when the six features are used. In all the scenarios presented in this section, the train, validation and test sets have been recalculated, again taking the last 20% for the test, and the last 15 % of the train for validating. To compare with the previous case, during all this section we have taken in the FL approach $N_e = 10$, and optimized in each case the optimal number of rounds.

In this scenario the results remain very similar to those with the original amount of data, which allows dismissing the effect of the amount of data to explain the better results obtained in River Enborne. The results for River Enborne continue being better than those for The Cut, which is attributable to the distribution of the data represented by the statistics shown in Table 1. Again, in this scenario the best performance for the Enborne test set is obtained with the federated architecture. The predictions obtained in each case and the observed values can be seen in Fig. 7.

The second scenario was based on the idea that the data are collected

Fig. 7. Prediction obtained for the test set of rivers Enborne and The Cut with each model analyzed. Data reduction: same dates.

Table 5

Summary of results in terms of MRE for train and test with the three approaches and using six features in a scenario with data reduced to a periodicity of 24 h for training, and testing every one hour.

Approach	Enborne		The Cut	
	MRE (train)	MRE (test)	MRE (train)	MRE (test)
IL	0.28	0.19	0.61	0.19
CL	0.21	0.25	0.51	0.19
FL (Enborne)	0.18	0.19	0.53	0.21
FL (The Cut)	0.18	0.19	0.53	0.21

with low frequency, having in mind that in many situations the monitoring is carried out manually. Therefore, the data were resampled with a frequency of 24 h (starting at 8 a.m.), simulating a sampling frequency of once a day. The observations were reduced to 617 for training in the case of *River Enborne* and 466 in *The Cut*. As one of the main advantages of soft-sensors is their ability to predict with high frequency, the predictions in the test set are made hourly. That is to say, in this scenario the possibility to use low frequency data to predict high frequency data is tested with the different approaches. The results obtained are detailed in Table 5.

The pronounced reduction of data has a negative effect on the train error in all the scenarios except for the FL approach in River Enborne. The penalty is more remarkable in The Cut, which is attributable to the lower capacity to learn about the pronounced peak. However, in this same scenario the test error is not practically penalized, which suggests that one observation a day can be enough, at least with the amount of

data available in this study. The optimum models considering the test error are obtained with the FL approaches for River Enborne, and with the CL one for The Cut. In addition, with respect to the train set the best results are obtained with the IL approach for both rivers, although in the case of River Enborne the FL approach is less overfitted, in other words it presents a higher generalization ability. Again, the predictions obtained in each case and the observed values can be seen in Fig. 8.

Following with the focus on the ability to predict at high resolution when few and widely spaced data are available, the next scenario uses data collected weekly for the training phase. Although this seems a drastic data reduction, this sampling scenario can be considered realistic enough, as it is not uncommon to perform manual sampling only once a week, where access to the sampling area is difficult or when there are limited resources. As in the previous example, the prediction with the test set is made hourly. The results obtained are detailed in Table 6.

Again in this case, the optimum for Enborne test set is reached with

Table 6

Summary of results in terms of MRE for train and test with the three approaches and using six features in a scenario with data reduced to a periodicity of one week. Prediction: every one hour.

Approach	Enborne		The Cut	
	MRE (train)	MRE (test)	MRE (train)	MRE (test)
IL	0.21	0.19	0.60	0.23
CL	0.22	0.24	0.48	0.26
FL (Enborne)	0.22	0.17	0.55	0.24
FL (The Cut)	0.22	0.17	0.57	0.23

Fig. 8. Prediction obtained for the test set of rivers Enborne and The Cut with each model analyzed. Data reduction: 24 h.

Fig. 9. Prediction obtained for the test set of rivers Enborne and The Cut with each model analyzed. Data reduction: 1 week.

the FL approach and for The Cut test set the FL approach performs better than IL and the same as CL. As for both training set, the optimum is obtained with the IL approach as expected. We can observe that the error for Enborne test set has decreased (using the FL approach for Enborne) with respect to the previous case despite the reduction of the number of training data, and we can conclude that in this case a reliable generalization to higher resolution data is obtained. This example clearly shows the generalization capacity of the FL approach in both cases with respect to the IL architecture (with the number of rounds in which the optimum was obtained for the validation of each river respectively) in cases of low resolution, closely spaced and few data. Finally, the predictions obtained in each case with this data reduction approach and the observed values are shown in Fig. 9.

Although the FL paradigm is often implemented when technical or privacy constraints prevent the centralization of data, in this work it has been seen its potential to enhance the generalization ability of a model, despite the fact of dealing with two clearly differentiated ecosystems. Thus, in this use case the data from the urban environment (The Cut) can help the generalization by including new and more varied casuistry to the more rural environment (River Enborne).

4. Conclusions and future work

ML and DL techniques show a strong capability to predict Chl concentrations based on basic hydro-physical variables that can be measured with robust and economic sensors. Additionally, one can introduce openly available meteorological features, which can have a notably positive impact.

Regarding the learning paradigm, IL normally provides better results on the training set, but combining the information of two sites in a FL paradigm can result in a higher generalization ability, as it has been demonstrated for the case of River Enborne. In the case of The Cut, in spite of not having achieved such advantage, the FL models are not notably penalized in comparison with the IL. Therefore, the FL paradigm can be recommended when data privacy issues occur, as well as any other difficulty to share the data from a site, without imposing a penalty on the performance of the models. Additionally, in all cases under this approach, the number of epochs multiplied by the number of rounds of the scheme is fewer than the number of epochs used by the IL or the CL, resulting in a lower computational cost and time. In general, in view of the results obtained in this use case, it is more convenient to apply the federated architecture instead of the centralized one in the case where it is intended to use the data from both zones.

These conclusions are maintained in the tested data reduction scenarios, where it has been also concluded that low frequency data can be used to predict high frequency data.

As already mentioned, a case study which such different ecosystems,

a priori is not the most suitable one for the application of the FL architecture, due to the different distribution of the data in both sites or clients. In a natural way, in order to have a larger amount of data for training, the use of the CL could arise. However, this paradigm has provided the poorest prediction ability in this study, concluding that the FL architecture is generally more convenient. The results show the interest of FL (especially compared to the centralized one) with special focus on its application when privacy or technical conditions require it, as well as in the case where there is little data available at a particular point, contributing to a better generalization of the models.

As future work, it is interesting the application of FL in a case with more clients, as well as to study the effect of the differences in data distributions across clients on the performance of FL models.

Data availability

All data used to conduct this study have been obtained from open data sources. Specifically, physico-chemical measurements for both rivers are available in the Environmental Information Data center platform <http://eidc.ceh.ac.uk/> of the center for Ecology and Hydrology (CEH) of the United Kingdom's Natural Environment Research Council. In addition, information on the meteorological variables used are obtained from the Photovoltaic Geographical Information System (PVGIS) https://re.jrc.ec.europa.eu/pvg_tools/en/.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

I have shared the link to the data in the article.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the support from the project AI4EOSC 'Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud' that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement number 101058593, as well as the support from Universidad de Cantabria and Consejería de Universidades, Igualdad, Cultura y Deporte del Gobierno de Cantabria via the 'Instrumentación y Ciencia de Datos para Sondar la Naturaleza del Universo' project.

Appendix

Flowchart

Fig. 10. Data preprocessing and model training, validation and testing flowcharts.

Additional error metrics

Beyond the analysis of the mean relative error (MRE) performed in Section 3, in order to choose a model for production implementation, it is essential to study other metrics to quantify the error. Therefore, Table 7 shows the results in terms of the mean absolute error (MAE) and the root mean square error (RMSE) in the four scenarios proposed in Table 3, both for the whole training set and for the test one.

Table 7

Summary of results in terms of MAE and RMSE for train and test with the three approaches and using six features.

	Enborne				The Cut			
	MAE (train)	MAE (test)	RMSE (train)	RMSE (test)	MAE (train)	MAE (test)	RMSE (train)	RMSE (test)
IL	0.50	0.55	0.70	0.76	1.71	0.85	3.39	1.26
CL	0.59	0.52	0.82	0.72	1.67	0.78	3.34	1.21
FL (Enborne)	0.59	0.55	0.85	0.73	2.35	1.08	5.01	1.49
FL (The Cut)	0.59	0.53	0.84	0.72	2.35	1.10	5.02	1.51

Prediction for the training set

According to the approaches shown in Table 3, Fig. 11 shows the predictions for both Enborne and The Cut training sets in the individual, centralized and FL cases. Regarding this last paradigm, in each case the approach with which the optimum of the MSE was obtained for the validation of each zone is shown.

Fig. 11. Prediction obtained for the train set of rivers Enborne and The Cut with each model (see Table 3).

Features distribution: Data reduction case

In the following, the distribution of the six features under study for the train set is shown by means of violin plots, in the three scenarios of data reduction exposed in Section 3. That is, reduction of the number of data so that only common dates are considered, taking only the data captured every 24 h and every one week in the third case.

Data reduction: same dates (train) Data reduction: 24 hours (train) Data reduction: 1 week (train)

Fig. 12. Rivers Enborne and The Cut. Features distribution: data reduction scenarios.

References

Aláez, F.M.B, Palenzuela, J.M.T, Spyarakos, E., Vilas, L.G., 2021. Machine learning methods applied to the prediction of pseudo-nitzschia spp. blooms in the Galician Rías Baixas (NW Spain). ISPRS Int. J. Geoinf. 10 (4) <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi10040199>.

Almuhtaram, H., Kibuye, FA., Ajjampur, S., Glover, CM., Hofmann, R., Gaget, V., Owen, C., Wert, E.C., Zamyadi, A., 2021. State of knowledge on early warning tools for cyanobacteria detection. Ecol. Indic. 133, 108442 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.108442>.

Barros, M.U.G., Wilson, A.E., Leitão, J.I.R., Pereira, S.P., Buley, R.P., Fernandez-Figueroa, E.G., Capelo-Neto, J., 2019. Environmental factors associated with toxic cyanobacterial blooms across 20 drinking water reservoirs in a semi-arid region of Brazil. Harmful Algae 86, 128–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2019.05.006>.

Barzegar, R., Aalami, M., Adamowski, J., 2020. Short-term water quality variable prediction using a hybrid CNN–LSTM deep learning model. Stoch. Environ. Res. Risk Assess. 34 (February), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00477-020-01776-2>.

Castrillo, M., Garcia, A.L., 2020. Estimation of high frequency nutrient concentrations from water quality surrogates using machine learning methods. Water Res. 172, 115490.

Chorus, I., Welker, M., 2021. Toxic Cyanobacteria in Water - a Guide to Their Public Health Consequences, Monitoring and Management, 2nd Ed. Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003081449>.

García Nieto, P.J., García-Gonzalo, E., Alonso Fernández, J.R., Díaz Muñoz, C., 2019. Water eutrophication assessment relied on various machine learning techniques: a case study in the Englishmen Lake (Northern Spain). Ecol. Modell. 404, 91–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2019.03.009>.

Glibert, P.M., 2020. Harmful algae at the complex nexus of eutrophication and climate change. Harmful Algae 91, 101583. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2019.03.001>.

Hinton, G., Deng, L., Yu, D., Dahl, G.E., Mohamed, A., Jaitly, N., Senior, A., et al., 2012. Deep neural networks for acoustic modeling in speech recognition: the shared views of four research groups. IEEE Signal Process. Mag. 29 (6), 82–97. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MSP.2012.2205597>.

Jin, J., Wells, S., De Liu, G.Y., Zhu, S., Ma, J., Yang, Z., 2019. Effects of water level fluctuation on thermal stratification in a typical tributary bay of Three Gorges Reservoir, China. PeerJ 7 (April). <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.6925>.

Khruschchev, S.S., Plyusnina, T.Y., Antal, T.K., Pogoyan, S.I., Riznichenko, G.Y., Rubin, A. B., 2022. Machine learning methods for assessing photosynthetic activity: environmental monitoring applications. Biophys. Rev. 14, 821–842. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12551-022-00982-2> pages.

- Kim, K.M., Ahn, J.H., 2022. Machine learning predictions of chlorophyll-a in the Han River Basin, Korea. Article J. Environ. Manag. 318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115636>.
- Krizhevsky, A., Sutskever, I., Hinton, G.E., 2017. ImageNet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. Commun. ACM 60 (6), 84–90. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3065386>.
- LeCun, Y., Bengio, Y., Hinton, G., 2015. Deep learning. Nature 521 (7553), 436–444. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14539>.
- Li, Q., Wen, Z., Wu, Z., Hu, S., Wang, N., Li, Y., Liu, X., He, B., 2021. A survey on federated learning systems: vision, hype and reality for data privacy and protection. IEEE Trans. Knowl. Data Eng. 35, 3347–3366. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2021.3124599>.
- Lundberg, S.M., Lee, S.I., 2017. A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. In: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, 30. Curran Associates, Inc, pp. 4765–4774 edited by I. Guyon, U. V. Luxburg, S. Bengio, H. Wallach, R. Fergus, S. Vishwanathan, and R. Garnett. <http://papers.nips.cc/paper/7062-a-unified-approach-to-interpreting-model-predictions.pdf>.
- McMahan, B., Moore, E., Ramage, D., Hampson, S., Aguera y Arcas, B., 2017. Communication-efficient learning of deep networks from decentralized data. In: Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics, 54, pp. 1273–1282 edited by A Singh and J Zhu. Proceedings of Machine Learning Research. PMLR. <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v54/mcmahan17a.html>.
- Mozo, A., Morón-López, J., Vakaruk, S., Pompa-Pernía, Á.G., González-Prieto, Á., Aguilar, J.A.P., Gómez-Canaval, S., Ortiz, J.M., 2022. Chlorophyll soft-sensor based on machine learning models for algal bloom predictions. Sci. Rep. 12 (1), 13529. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-17299-5>.
- Nair, A., Hykkerud, A., Ratnaweera, H., 2022. Estimating phosphorus and COD concentrations using a hybrid soft sensor: a case study in a norwegian municipal wastewater treatment plant. Water 14 (3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14030332> (Basel).
- Park, Y., Cho, K.H., Park, J., Cha, S.M., Kim, J.H., 2015. Development of early-warning protocol for predicting chlorophyll-a concentration using machine learning models in freshwater and estuarine reservoirs, Korea. Sci. Total Environ. 502, 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.09.005>.
- Sáinz-Pardo Díaz, J., García, Á.L., 2023. Study of the performance and scalability of federated learning for medical imaging with intermittent clients. Neurocomputing 518, 142–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2022.11.011>.
- Shuvo, A., O'Reilly, C., Blagrove, K., Ewins, C., Filazzola, A., Gray, D., Mahdian, O., Moslenko, L., Quinlan, R., Sharma, S., 2021. Total phosphorus and climate are equally important predictors of water quality in lakes. Aquat. Sci. 83 (January) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00027-021-00776-w>.
- United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, (DESA).. The sustainable development goals report 2022. <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2022/The-Sustainable-Development-Goals-Report-2022.pdf>.
- Visser, P.M., Verspagen, J.M.H., Sandrini, G., Stal, L.J., Matthijs, H.C.P., Davis, T.W., Paerl, H.W., Huisman, J., 2016. How rising CO₂ and global warming may stimulate harmful cyanobacterial blooms. Harmful Algae 54, 145–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2015.12.006>.
- Wade, A.J., Palmer-Felgate, E.J., Halliday, S.J., Skeffington, R.A., Loewenthal, M., Jarvie, H.P., Bowes, M.J., et al., 2012. Hydrochemical processes in Lowland Rivers: insights from *in situ*, high-resolution monitoring. Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci. 16 (11), 4323–4342. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-16-4323-2012>.
- Wang, R., Kim, J.H., Li, M.H., 2021. Predicting stream water quality under different urban development pattern scenarios with an interpretable machine learning approach. Article Sci. Total Environ. 761. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144057>.